

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Research on countermeasures for the promotion of employees' digital innovation capability against the background of enterprise digital transformation

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 22(01), 1887–1896

Publication history: Received on 14 March 2024; revised on 24 April 2024; accepted on 26 April 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.22.1.1286>

Abstract

Improving employees' digital innovation capability is an important factor in the realization of enterprise digital transformation. However, at present, the supply of digital talent is far from sufficient, the improvement of employees' digital innovation capabilities is slow, and there are few methods within enterprises to improve the digital innovation capabilities of employees, which has led to a shortage of digital innovation talent and constraints in the digital transformation of enterprises. Based on these questions, we use procedural grounded theory for analysis. The analysis shows that the enterprise lacks incentives for employees, lacks diversified training methods, lacks orderly organizational management and has a good corporate atmosphere. Based on the above findings, we analyze and discuss four aspects—the incentive mechanism, employee training, organizational management, and corporate climate—and propose countermeasures to enhance the digital innovation capability of employees to better empower employees and the enterprise.

Keywords: Digital Transformation; Digital Innovation Capability; Programmatic Roots; Countermeasure Research

1. Introduction

With the new technological revolution and the rapid development of industrial transformation, the global economy is in an unprecedented period of orbital change, and with the development of information technology and the rise of the digital economy, the state's support for the digital transformation of enterprises has increased, and multiple laws have been promulgated. However, improving employees' digital innovation capability has a great promoting effect on the development of enterprise digitalization. Employees can use advanced technologies and tools to enable the enterprise's data to be processed and analyzed quickly and efficiently, thereby providing a scientific basis for the enterprise's decision-making, improving the enterprise's production efficiency, reducing costs and optimizing business processes. Currently, many people, such as Jun Ma and Mingjie Guo, mainly start with the digital transformation of enterprises. Error! Reference source not found. To study how to accelerate enterprise digitalization, Zhang Tianxia and Sun Minzhi discussed why digital talent is important to enterprises from the perspective of enterprises' need for digital Error! Reference source not found. talent. There are few studies on how employees enhance their digital innovation capabilities, especially improvement countermeasures. Therefore, this paper focuses on employees and discusses how to enhance their digital innovation capabilities to compensate for the deficiencies of previous studies and to provide better education. solve the problem.

The rapid development of enterprise digital transformation can significantly enhance the market value of enterprises [3]. Digital transformation can promote an increase in the scale and quality of human capital allocation of enterprises by improving information transparency and internal management capabilities and increasing innovation investment [4]. Promote certain changes within the enterprise to better adapt to the direction of social development. Talent is an

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important strategic resource for national rejuvenation and winning the initiative in international competition. Improving employees' digital innovation capability plays a key role in promoting the digital transformation of enterprises and winning new advantages in competition [5]. To meet the internal change and development requirements of enterprises, a large amount of talent with digital innovation capabilities is needed to perform corresponding higher-level tasks and coordinate the better development of enterprises. Enterprises need to adopt a series of measures to enhance the digital innovation capability of employees and better support their development. Enterprises should be encouraged to build more open, shared and connected training mechanisms. Digitization involves not only the application and promotion of digital technology but also comprehensive changes in organizational management and talent development. Digitalization puts new requirements on employee capabilities. The cultivation of employees' digital capabilities can help employees address the opportunities and challenges of digitalization and promote the improvement of individual performance and organizational development [6]. The digital innovation capability of enterprise employees is the source of motivation for the development of enterprise digital transformation. The improvement of employees' digital innovation capability enables employees to better adapt to the enterprise development model, keep up with the speed of enterprise development, and promote the enterprise digitalization process with a broader vision, a more practical spirit, and more comprehensive abilities [7]. Through the analysis of the digital transformation of enterprises and the promotion of the digital innovation capability of employees, it can be seen that there is a mutual influence between the two, which provides an important research direction for the present study. Therefore, the author analyzes the digital transformation of enterprises and the enhancement of the digital innovation capabilities of employees and then combines the two for further in-depth analysis to explore countermeasures for improving employees' digital innovation capabilities.

1.1. Relationship analysis

The improvement of employees' digital innovation capability is affected by various factors, which makes the study of improvement countermeasures more complicated, including the influences of the intrinsic relationship between the enterprise and the employees themselves and the relationship between the individual employees and the enterprise as a whole (Figure 1). They coordinate and interact with each other. Therefore, when studying countermeasures to enhance the digital innovation capability of employees, the analysis is divided into three parts: the factors for improving employees' own digital innovation capability, the factors for improving the digital innovation capability of employees, and the combined influence of employees and the enterprise.

Figure 1 Business-employee relationship

1.2. Factors for the improvement of employees' digital innovation capabilities

In general, the improvement of employees' digital innovation capabilities will be limited by their own abilities. For employees who lack their own knowledge reserves and have fixed thinking methods, the improvement of digital

innovation capabilities is slower than that of other employees with active thinking and rich knowledge reserves. Therefore, exercising employees' innovative thinking and independent learning ability is particularly critical for improving their digital innovation ability.

The improvement of employees' digital innovation capabilities comes from the improvement of comprehensive abilities in part. Employees with fixed thinking styles should cultivate their innovative thinking and maintain their curiosity, while employees with weak knowledge reserves and without a good innovation foundation should train their independent thinking. They can improve their cognitive level, expand their thinking and paths, and equip them with the ability to innovate independently. With these diversified methods, the abilities of employees will be enhanced. The improvement of employees' digital innovation capabilities includes the improvement of individual employees' abilities and the improvement of the teamwork of employees as a whole. Therefore, in an efficient and collaborative team, the innovation ability of employees is more tapped and brought into play, which better improves the digital innovation of employees.

1.3. Factors underlying the improvement of employees' digital innovation capability

Improving employees' digital innovation capability is the key to enterprise transformation. Against the background of enterprise digital transformation, the influence of the enterprise on its employees has become increasingly evident. Digital transformation has made it more convenient and efficient to acquire and process information within the enterprise and has enabled employees to obtain a variety of information more quickly and use this information for more accurate and accurate results. Comprehensive and accurate decision-making can promote the development of enterprises. In the process of development, enterprises also pay more attention to employees' learning and training opportunities, sense of self-fulfillment, and challenges. Enterprises try to provide a better innovation environment and conditions for employees so that employees can work harder to serve the enterprise and promote its development. To promote innovation and development, the digital innovation capability of employees should be improved.

1.4. The combined influence of employees and the enterprise

An enterprise and its employees are a win-win relationship that includes cooperation, partnerships, benefit sharing and risk sharing, and employees are an important part of the enterprise. For an enterprise, the quality of the work of its employees affects the speed and quality of the enterprise's development, and the enterprise will use a series of measures to help its employees improve. For employees, the prospect of enterprise development affects their salaries, future expectations and trust in the enterprise. Employees will try their best to improve the quality of the work they complete to promote the progress of the enterprise. They are a community of interests, undertakings, and destiny. For both enterprises and employees, it is necessary to enhance the digital innovation capability of employees.

2. Category refinement

Based on the above analysis, through procedural grounded theory analysis, the important subjects for the promotion of employees' digital innovation capabilities are extracted, and starting from the important subjects, the relevant countermeasures for the promotion of employees' digital innovation capabilities are analyzed.

2.1. Study design and data collation

The improvement of employees' digital innovation capability will be affected by the subjective factors of employees themselves. Employees' views on the enterprise, communication with colleagues and trust in themselves all contain employees' own thoughts. Programmatic grounded theory, on the other hand, is based on the original sentences and data and further systematic analysis, mining construction, and development, which can well reflect the subjectivity of employees and explore the core nature of employees' promotion of digital innovation ability. Understand countermeasures. The present study was conducted mainly through online and field visits.

There are numerous plans for improving the digital innovation capability of employees on the internet. Therefore, the data obtained in this study are mainly based on the personal accounts of the interviewees and changes in corporate policies online. The specific process is as follows. First, through information collection, we understood the policies adopted by most enterprises in response to digital transformation and changes in employees' positions. Second, we asked employees how they felt about their company through video interviews and private message chats and at the same time integrated the data. Then, by using the project title as the key search word, the obtained data and text are supplemented by using relevant websites and news databases. Finally, we will conduct an interview and survey. During January and February 2024, we will interview employees in different companies about their feelings and the company's

treatment of employees to obtain first-hand information and integrate all the abovementioned data to better refine the scope.

2.2. Open coding

Open coding is the first stage of programmatic grounding research. It is necessary to define, refine, and achieve conceptualization and categorization of the original data ^[8], which is an important part of grounded theory data analysis. The samples were selected according to the research purpose, and the original sentences and the main data obtained were analyzed to extract the main content and deficiencies. After categorization, a total of 10 categories were extracted—specific original sentences, concepts and categories (partial)—as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Open coding

original statement	conceptualisation	generalisation
1. The company seldom gives out awards, certificates, merits and commendations. 2. When evaluating advanced and exemplary employees, the company pays more attention to the employees' work performance and ignores the work results. 3. I like to do things by myself, I don't like to do things together as a team, it's a bit troublesome. 4. Doing the same thing every day, with little novelty.	Low number of staff recognition Ignoring motivational goals Lack of team spirit	Lack of mental stimulation
5. The company pays out fewer bonuses and items 6. Wages are fixed and rarely promoted 7. Provide few opportunities for promotion and development, and general welfare benefits	Small changes in remuneration Lack of diversified incentives	Lack of remuneration incentives
4. Doing the same thing every day, with little novelty 8. Confused about the company and their career prospects 9. Lack of understanding of the company's culture 10. Lack of self-realisation in the company 11. Feeling that they are not suitable to work in this company.	Few corporate cultural activities Lack of employee trust in the organisation Conflict of ideas between employees and the organisation	Lack of cultural incentives
4. Doing the same thing every day, with fewer novelties. 12. When you arrive at a new job, you are not familiar with some of the work and need to learn by yourself 13. The company has fewer training opportunities and limited resources for employees. 14. Companies focus on the training of professional knowledge of employees, ignoring other work-related skills training 15. The company rarely trains its employees	Lack of diversified training modalities Low employee adaptability to the workplace Corporate training as a whole deviates from its parts	Lack of staff skills training
15. The company rarely trains its employees 16. The quality and working attitude of some colleagues and leaders are not friendly. 17. Work well in the company, and try not to care about other things 18. New employees are a bit panicky 19. Just joined the company do not know whether it can do a good job	The quality of the staff is average Employee mindset is not well aligned Lack of establishment of professionalism	Lack of staff quality training
16. The quality and work attitude of some colleagues and leaders are not friendly 20. The relationship between responsibility and authority at work is not clear, and sometimes it is necessary to do other people's work 21. Sometimes, the person in charge of looking for specialised can not be found 22. Some job descriptions are incomplete, do not know what to do	Average management attitude Unclear lines of responsibility Lack of clear workflows and common channels	Lack of clarity on mandated duties and responsibilities
20. The relationship between work responsibility and authority is not clear, sometimes need to do other people's work 23. The company decision-making time is very long, do not know when to transfer positions 24. Information does not flow, do not know when to change positions 25. The departments are not familiar with each other, seldom coordinate work	Long and slow adjustment cycles Lack of effective tools to obtain information	Untimely organisational adjustments
26. Tasks are communicated with confusion and unclear objectives 27. Some people lack team spirit, often do their own, it is difficult to coordinate effectively 28. Communication between upper and lower levels is not convenient, there is no good and clear division of labour. 29. Colleague relationship is general, lack of effective communication between upper and lower levels, slow progress of work.	Lack of clarity of objectives and mandates Lack of effective tracking mechanisms Teams don't work together, communication barriers	Lack of effective organisational functioning
30. Office design and decoration with more cool colours 31. Less green, there is a sense of dullness 32. The work office is not very big	Office environment is colourful and not very regional	Lack of effective shaping of the environmental climate
29. Colleague relations are average, lack of effective communication between upper and lower levels, slow progress of work 33. The internal environment of work is very stressful, everyone is in the rolls 34. Some leaders draw a big cake and can't talk about the real place	Leaders use the wrong methods and do not motivate their employees well Stressful working environment The average psychological fit between colleagues can easily lead to internal conflict and failure to achieve organisational goals.	Lack of effective moulding of the work atmosphere

2.3. Spindle encoding

In the second stage of programmatic grounded research, spindle coding requires in-depth analysis of the initial categories to identify and establish causal, correlated, and structural relationships between different initial categories and clusters and names them accordingly. Subcategories and main categories are extracted to develop strict category properties and levels [9]. For example, lack of spiritual motivation, lack of salary incentives, and lack of cultural incentives were clustered into the main categories of incentive mechanisms, indicating that enterprises must have a complete incentive mechanism to improve the digital innovation capability of their employees.

The abovementioned categorized sentences are extracted and clustered to form four main categories: incentive mechanism, employee training, organization management, and corporate climate. These main categories are further explained, and the subcategories of the main category and the related subcategories are extracted. Corresponding connotation. Table 2 shows the details.

Table 2 Spindle codes

main category	subcategory	Connotation of subcategories
incentive	Spiritual Incentives	A way for companies to motivate people to challenge difficulties, increase confidence and boost morale, either psychologically or behaviourally
	Compensation Incentives	Remuneration based on individual employee performance
	Cultural Incentives	Utilise the unique power of corporate culture to motivate employees to act towards the desired goals of the company.
Staff Training	Employee Skills Training	Enterprises train employees in job competencies for the needs of their jobs
	Employee Quality Training	Enterprises require digital aspects of employees, mainly psychological quality, personal work attitude, work habits and other digital training
Organisational management	Organisational Design	Planning and consideration of the organisation's structure and activities in the light of the organisation's objectives.
	Organisation Operation	A series of dynamic processes that an organisation undertakes to achieve its goals and perform its functions
	Organisational Adjustment	
working atmosphere	Environment	The atmosphere created by the design and decoration of the office space
	Work atmosphere	The spreading influence of the words and actions of surrounding team members. Including interpersonal relationships and leadership styles

2.4. Selective coding

In the third stage of programmatic grounding research, selective encoding involves the selection of a core generic concept from all the discovered concept categories and the gathering of related secondary generic concepts through continuous analysis. The purpose is to sort out the core categories and establish logical relationships between the core categories and other categories by describing the “story line” of the phenomenon. Based on the above analysis, the core category is identified as countermeasures for improving the digital innovation capability of employees against the background of enterprise digital transformation. Overall, against the background of digital transformation, enterprises should accelerate their internal information acquisition and processing and provide better incentive mechanisms, employee training, organizational management and corporate atmosphere for employees. Based on the various resources provided by the enterprise, employees improve their digital innovation capabilities and further empower the enterprise to promote better development. Under the interaction of a virtuous circle, the development of employees and the enterprise is promoted. In part, the incentive mechanism provided by the enterprise will effectively reward employees, satisfy their sense of self-fulfillment, and make employees more actively involved in their work and improve their abilities. The employee training provided by the enterprise can expand the scope of employees’ knowledge, technical ability, and thinking ways, etc., to better develop the limits of employees’ abilities, to give full play to the role of employees, and to better promote the development of the enterprise; the complete organization management of the enterprise can better enable employees to carry out their work in an orderly manner and better integrate positions with the abilities of employees. The enterprise provides a good atmosphere that will make employees happy, reduce their psychological stress, and stimulate their digital innovation ability.

On this basis, based on the original data and existing research, we construct a theoretical model of countermeasures for the promotion of employees’ digital innovation capability in the context of enterprise digital transformation, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Theoretical model of countermeasures to enhance employees' digital innovation capability in the context of enterprise digital transformation

2.5. Theoretical saturation test

The test of saturation refers to the moment when additional data cannot be obtained to continue to develop the characteristics of a certain category. This study used the initial categories generated from the interview materials, literature, and online videos of a number of interviewees as the standard for theoretical saturation testing. The above data were shuffled and numbered randomly. No new categories were discovered during the coding process. To maintain the rigor of the study, we conducted another test to randomly interview employees. During the coding process of the newly added data, no new coding or the emergence of categories was observed. Therefore, it can be determined that the theory in the present study has reached saturation, and the theoretical saturation is relatively high and has a certain reliability.

3. Analysis of results and development countermeasures

Through the abovementioned coding process of procedurally grounded theory, the present study extracted the corresponding main categories and core categories and constructed a theoretical model of countermeasures for the promotion of employees' digital innovation capability against the background of enterprise digital transformation. It can be seen from the model that the promotion of employees' digital innovation capability is a complex issue that involves two major subjects, the enterprise and the employees, as well as the relationship between these two subjects. The improvement of employees' digital innovation capability is the result of the comprehensive action of multiple factors. Specifically, there are four methods for enhancing the digital innovation capability of employees: the enterprise provides an incentive mechanism, the enterprise provides employee training, the enterprise optimizes organizational management, and the enterprise creates a corporate atmosphere. These four methods interact and influence each other.

(1) The relationship between the two main subjects, the enterprise and the employees. In essence, the enterprise and its employees have a cooperative partnership that depends on each other and promotes each other. Enterprises need the skills and wisdom of their employees to promote their development, and employees need the platform and resources of the enterprise to achieve their career development. The four aspects of the incentive mechanism provided by the enterprise—employee training, organizational management, and the corporate atmosphere—affect employees in two ways. One is the enterprise's influence (partial) on employees under the action of these countermeasures, and the other is the employee's countermeasures. Table 3 shows the impacts (parts) of these countermeasures on us.

Table 3 Influence of internal and external factors on employees

	Business Impact on Employees	Employees' impact on themselves
incentive	Stimulate employees' sense of competition and innovation, which helps to develop their potential and bring out their greater abilities Helps to provide comprehensive employee quality and work enthusiasm by rewarding good behaviours and criticising bad behaviours Motivate employees to learn and upskill, better adapt to change and challenges, and improve digital innovation	Better self-regulation, increasing their own morale, compensating for shortcomings and motivating them to take measures to achieve the incentive targets Provide work incentives for better access to rewards and recognition Have honour and learn to promote yourself
Staff Training	Improve employee skills, efficiency and satisfaction, enhance employee benefits and career development opportunities Helps provide team cohesion and better interpersonal relationships Enhancing the professional competence of employees to meet the development needs of enterprises and society	Enhancement of one's own knowledge storage level, way of thinking an practical ability, and enhancement of one's competitiveness Empowering employees with digital innovation capabilities to keep pace with industry developments Competence enhancement provides wider scope for career development and stimulates interest in new knowledge
Organisational management	Keeping employees organised and maximising their development and value Provide work norms and guidelines for individual staff development and career advancement Timely grasp of various kinds of information, effectively take strong measures against various problems	More aware of planning and time Learn to integrate better into the team, understand leadership decisions and implement them better Know and position yourself more accurately and work to improve your competencies
Corporate atmosphere	Make employees feel respected Enabling employees to make conscious changes to deliver productivity and digital innovation Enhancing Employee Belonging and Cohesion	Emotional stability, pleasure, satisfaction with one's work, good interpersonal relations A sense of belonging and identity to the enterprise, that the enterprise is community with oneself Work proceeds in harmony and psychological stress at work is reduced

The enterprise provides an incentive mechanism. The incentive mechanism refers to the process of maximizing the commitment of employees to the organization and the work through specific methods and management systems. The good use of the incentive mechanism can encourage employees to make continuous progress and innovation so that they can be more motivated and focused on completing work tasks, forming a benign competitive environment and better promoting the long-term development of the enterprise. From an enterprise's perspective, the lack of an incentive mechanism cannot enable the enterprise to better play the facilitating and weakening role of the incentive mechanism. Therefore, the enterprise needs to correctly develop an effective incentive mechanism, clarify the needs of employees at all levels and in each position, and determine what kind of incentive mechanism can effectively meet the needs of employees. Therefore, under the dual functions of physical and mental mechanisms, the digital innovation ability of employees is improved, and a certain behavior of employees that meets the expectations of the enterprise is repeatedly reinforced and continuously enhanced. For example, rewards include performance awards, profit sharing, promotions and salary increases, travel, honor, participation in enterprise management, etc. Enterprises need to differentiate these methods and combine them with the assessment system to better stimulate competition among employees. awareness For example, starting from Maslow's need theory (Figure 2), at different levels of needs, the needs of employees are met, and while their needs are met, employees' abilities will increase accordingly, and further development will occur. Therefore, improving the incentive mechanism can stimulate improvements in employees' digital innovation ability based on different needs.

Figure 3 Application of Maslow's Needs Theory

The enterprise provides employee training. Employee training refers to the management activities in which an organization conducts purposeful and planned training and training for its employees in various ways to meet the needs of carrying out business and cultivating talent. Employee training can improve the skills, efficiency and satisfaction of employees; solve the problems of employees' weak ideological innovation ability and applied innovation ability and single innovation methods from the perspective of employees' own abilities; increase their own knowledge reserves; and improve their practical ability, comprehensive quality and work ability. attitudes and habits to solve problems in an optimal manner. From the perspective of the enterprise, it can help the enterprise attract, retain and train excellent talent and enhance its core competitiveness to better improve its digital innovation ability and promote its competitiveness. For employee training, enterprises should train them in management skills, team building, communication skills, professional abilities, etc., and learn to let them find the best solution from multiple paths, change their way of thinking, and improve their innovative thinking ability. Allow employees to develop and enhance their abilities and better adapt to the rapid development of enterprise digital transformation.(4) The enterprise optimizes its organization and management. Enterprise organization management is an arrangement for responsible institutions and personnel arrangements constituted according to certain rules and procedures to effectively allocate limited resources within the enterprise and achieve certain common goals. Goal. Organizational management should determine the activities required by organizational goals, classify them according to the principles of specialization and division of labor, and create corresponding jobs by category. The effective management of an organization can compensate for deficiencies, assist management, enhance communication and correct management. In organizing the management of employees, the enterprise should clarify the rules and regulations, clarify the mutual responsibilities among employees and the work handover between the superiors and the subordinates, and clarify the supervision and inspection standards for the work so that every employee can carry out the work in an orderly manner and develop to the maximum extent. and play the value of employees. Enterprises should establish a performance evaluation index system and effective communication management. Before the work is completed, the enterprise should investigate the work quality of employees, reward excellent employees and warn reluctant employees. Communication management includes oral expression, written expression, document delivery, and meeting discussion. Effective communication will enable all members of the organization to keep abreast of the problems and situations the organization is facing and take timely measures. Organizational management allows employees to grasp the latest data in real time, solve new problems together, and perform the work of the enterprise in a structured and efficient manner. In this process, the abilities of employees are developed and enhanced.

The enterprise creates a corporate atmosphere. It is very important for an enterprise to establish and maintain a positive and healthy corporate atmosphere. A positive corporate atmosphere can stimulate the work enthusiasm and creativity of employees, while a sluggish corporate atmosphere will make employees unable to mention their jobs. Momentum. Corporate climate can be divided into working climate and environmental climate. The working atmosphere is an atmosphere and environment that is gradually formed in a unit. It has certain characteristics and can be perceived and identified by unit members. It requires leaders and enterprises to listen to the voices of employees, pay attention to the feelings and thoughts of employees, and let employees feel that their opinions and suggestions are respected and valued. This will enable employees to consciously change themselves to improve their work efficiency and digital innovation ability. In the working atmosphere, a positive culture needs to be established by setting up employee care programs and organizing team-building activities to enhance employees' sense of belonging and cohesion. At the same time, leaders should lead by example and play the role of role models so that employees feel the company's care and support for them, thus making them more devoted to the work and more willing to stay in the enterprise for a long time and contributing their talents and wisdom to the development of the enterprise. The environmental atmosphere refers to the style and sentiment reflected by the enterprise through the intuitive and explicit environment. When employees work hard, a good corporate environment can make employees happier and more willing to continue to work, reducing the risk of long working hours. enormous psychological pressure. Enterprises should adjust the working environment according to the needs of different departments, such as by adding green plants, elegant hanging ornaments, and meaningful photographs. The working atmosphere and environmental atmosphere well shape the corporate atmosphere. A good corporate atmosphere can close the distance between the enterprise and its employees, unleash the potential of employees, enable them to devote more wholeheartedly to their work, and better regulate their employees. Emotional and work attitudes, health and mental states improve the digital innovation ability of employees.

4. Conclusions

Against the background of enterprise digital transformation, the requirements of enterprises to keep up with the development of the times and the demand for value creation are highly inflated, while employees play an important role in the digital transformation of enterprises and are an important driving force of enterprises. To better develop the enterprise, employees need to have digital innovation capabilities as well as high professional knowledge and skills to

create value for the enterprise. This paper focused on countermeasures for the promotion of employees' digital innovation capability, the causes of the lack of employees' digital innovation capability and the analysis of the relationship between employees and the enterprise. The main conclusions were drawn as follows:

- Factors for improving employees' digital innovation capability. The improvement of employees' digital innovation capability is in line with the rapid development of the enterprise digital economy. Employees need an environment and policies that improve their digital innovation capabilities to stimulate their subjective initiative and empower them. The improvement in employees' digital innovation capability is due to the following factors. First, the incentive mechanism improves the enthusiasm of employees, which strengthens their interest in employee training and has an adverse effect on their participation in the incentive mechanism. In the context of effective organizational management and a positive and friendly corporate atmosphere, the improvement of employees' digital innovation capability has entered a virtuous circle and grown steadily.
- Enhance the digital innovation ability of employees to create new value. The improvement of employees' digital innovation capability expands the development direction and prospects of the enterprise and its employees, enables them to better innovate technologies and products, increases their social contributions, and makes the enterprise stand out among the numerous competitors because the employees and the enterprise are interdependent. The improvement of employees' innovation ability and the continuous updating of knowledge and skills will push the enterprise to carry out continuous reform and development to create value, thus creating new value.
- Employees' digital innovation empowers the enterprise. The improvement of employees' digital innovation ability makes employees the main body of innovation and entrepreneurship. An increase in employees' abilities indirectly promotes the development of enterprises. The development of enterprises will in turn provide a better environment for employees, empowering the development of enterprises in a virtuous circle. The development of an enterprise will indirectly affect the development of surrounding enterprises. They will learn from and improve their own internal working forms and methods to better adapt to the development of the enterprise and society and maintain a good operation mode.

4.1. Theory and Practice Implications

First, scholars mostly focus on the importance of digital talent for enterprises or how to accelerate enterprise digitalization. There are few studies on internal employees in enterprises. This paper studies methods and countermeasures for the promotion of employees' digital innovation capabilities from the perspective of employees and proposes that incentives, employee training, organizational management and corporate atmosphere are the main factors for improving employees' digital innovation ability. Through further analysis of these factors, the understanding of the influence of the enterprise on its employees and the influence of employees on themselves has deepened the improvement of employees' digital innovation ability to a certain extent. related theories. Second, this study focused on countermeasures for improving employees' digital innovation capabilities against the background of enterprise digital transformation and aimed to address the problems of the slow improvement of employees' digital innovation capabilities and the obstacles to improvement. Therefore, this study investigated the relationship between employees and enterprises and examined mutual promotion between them. Based on the premise of analyzing the relationship between the two, the impact of the implementation of enterprise policies on employees and the impact of the improvement of employees' digital innovation capabilities on the enterprise are discussed. Development gradually forms a virtuous circular relationship, which promotes the improvement of employees' digital innovation ability and empowers employees and the enterprise. This provides new ideas and methods to better solve the problems of employees' weak digital innovation ability and the obstruction of enterprise development motivation. It enriches the research theory on the relationship between the improvement of employees' ability and enterprises.

Regarding the above four areas—the incentive mechanism, employee training, organizational management and corporate climate—while conducting research on these four areas, we understand the role and value of promoting the improvement of employees' digital innovation ability. Based on the abovementioned aspects, we propose corresponding countermeasures in combination with specific problems to enhance the digital innovation capability of employees. This approach provides effective solutions and countermeasures for other enterprises to better solve actual problems and is more applicable and practical.

4.2. Limitations and prospects

This paper used grounded theory to select the views of the employees of a number of enterprises about their enterprise, which has certain universality and authenticity. However, the selected enterprises are scattered, most are concentrated in Zhejiang, and there are fewer enterprises in other provinces, so the conclusion is meaningful. Certain regional natures. The products produced by each enterprise are mostly different. There are also regional influences. There is no guarantee that this conclusion is applicable to all enterprises. The use of this method by enterprises needs actual

verification. In future research, we can collect the views of employees of different types of enterprises in various regions, collect more detailed data, analyze and summarize how different types of employees enhance digital innovation capabilities, and further deepen and expand the relevant research.

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